

H FNMTC - BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2019
RGN 21:: RGN 121
TIME ALLOWED: 2HOURS
OBJECTIVES

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

QUESTION ONE

Baby Tashia is a 2-year old patient admitted to the Paediatric ward where you are a student nurse on duty. She is diagnosed with severe Malaria and exhibiting **pyrexia**.

- a. Explain **FIVE (5)** roles of the skin in regulating this temperature to normal - 5 marks
- b. State from **deep to superficial** the layers of the epidermis in a thick skin - 4 marks
- c. Tabulate **FOUR (4)** differences each between eccrine sweat glands and apocrine sweat glands in the human skin - 4 marks
- d. State any **FOUR (4)** age-related changes in the skin - 4 marks
- e. Outline **THREE (3)** sources of skin color - 3 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. With an aid of a well labeled diagram (**more than half a page**), describe the **internal anatomy** of the kidney
 - i. Diagram - 4 marks
 - ii. Describe - 5 marks
- b. Outline 4 constituents of urine - 2 marks
- c. State the processes that parathyroid hormone uses to promote an increase in blood calcium level - 3 marks
- d. Explain how the Renin-Angiotensin-Aldosterone System regulate blood pressure - 6 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. Describe the mechanism of inspiration - 6 marks
- b. Explain **THREE (3)** physiological variables that affect respiration - 6 marks
- c. State the activities involved in gas conditioning - 3 marks
- d. Mention any **THREE (3)** accessory muscles of respiration - 3 marks
- e. Outline the epithelium that lines the following: - 2 marks
 - i. Trachea
 - ii. Alveoli of the lungs

QUESTION FOUR

- a. Study the diagram below carefully and identify the parts labeled I – X - 6 marks

- b. Mention any **FIVE (5)** components of bile - 5 marks
- c. Ms Jumo took a plate of plain rice and fish as lunch, explain to Stella how the digestion of the fish will give her amino acid (explain the digestion and absorption of protein) - 5 marks
- d. Outline the function of the following: - 4 marks
 - i. Cholecystokinin
 - ii. Insulin
 - iii. Goblet cell
 - iv. Parietal cell

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC, BERKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS- DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - DECEMBER 2018
RGN 21/RM 16 (RGN 111/RMD 1110 ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY 1
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

You have been assigned by your ward in charge to care for Mr. Owusu who has multiple broken bones of the upper and lower limbs.

- | | |
|--|-----------|
| a. Describe the macroscopic structure of a typical long bone. | - 8 marks |
| b. Describe the following types of bone cells | |
| i. Osteoblasts | - 2 marks |
| ii. Osteocytes | - 2 marks |
| iii. Osteogenic cells | - 2 marks |
| c. Explain four (4) factors that can contribute to the healing process of Mr. Owusu. | 4 marks |
| d. Mention any four (4) parts of a typical vertebra | - 2 marks |

Question Two

During the vacation period, your mother aged 65, asked you to check her blood pressure as she was experiencing dull headache. You recorded 180/100mmHg, which was way higher than her usual blood pressure of 120/80mmHg.

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|--|-----------|
| a. Define blood pressure | - 2 marks |
| b. Enumerate eight (8) factors that might influence blood pressure | - 4 marks |
| c. Describe the three (3) layers of the heart. | - 6 marks |
| d. Briefly describe the following heart valves | |
| i. Tricuspid valve | - 3 marks |
| ii. Bicuspid valve | - 3 marks |
| iii. Pulmonary valve | - 2 marks |

Question Three

Baby Peal is a 3 year-old patient admitted at the Paediatric ward where you are a student nurse on duty. She has high body temperature of 38.3 °C.

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|--|----------|
| a. Define homeostasis | - 2marks |
| b. State and explain the components of homeostasis | - 6marks |
| c. Explain how Baby Pearl's high body temperature could be reversed through homeostasis. | - 6marks |
| d. Mention any six (6) variables controlled by homeostasis | - 6marks |

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION- DECEMBER 2017
RGN 20 & RM 15, (RGN 111/ RMD 111) ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY I
TIME ALLOWED:2 HOURS
ESSAY

Instructions

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

- | | | | |
|--|-------------|---|---------|
| a. With the aid of a well labeled diagram covering half a page, describe the posterior view of the femur | | - | |
| | Diagram | - | 4 marks |
| | Description | - | 6 marks |
| b. State the bones forming the cranium | | - | 3 marks |
| c. Mention any three(3) functions of synovial fluid | | - | 3 marks |
| d. Outline the structures entering and leaving the spleen at the hilum | | - | 4marks |

Question Two

- | | | | |
|---|--|---|---------|
| a. State five (5) components of the lymphatic system | | - | |
| | | - | 5 marks |
| b. Outline any four (4) cells in connective tissue | | - | 4 marks |
| c. Describe the abdominal cavity | | - | 7 marks |
| d. Explain 3 differences between pinocytosis and phagocytosis | | - | 3 marks |

Question Three

- | | | | |
|--|--|---|---------|
| a. Identify three (3) characteristics each of skeletal , smooth and cardiac muscles | | - | |
| | | - | 9 marks |
| b. Mention four(4) functions of muscles | | - | 4 marks |
| c. Describe five (5) ways through which skeletal muscles are named and give one (1) example each | | - | 5 marks |
| d. Enumerate any four (4) muscles of the abdominal wall | | - | 2 marks |

Question Four

- | | | | |
|---|--|---|---------|
| a. Describe the valves of the heart | | - | |
| | | - | 8 marks |
| b. Enumerate four(4) functions of blood | | - | 4 marks |
| c. Define heart rate | | - | 1 mark |
| d. Mention six (6) factors affecting heart rate | | - | 3 marks |
| e. Explain why in the ABO and Rhesus blood grouping systems, blood group O- are considered universal donors | | - | 4 marks |

NMTC-BEREKUM/ST MARY'S CAMPUS-DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-DECEMBER, 2015
HRGN 010 /HDW10 ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY I
TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the questions carefully and provide only the relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provide beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will attract any mark

Question One

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|--|---|---------|
| a. Draw a large (1/3 of a page) labelled diagram of the nerve cell (Myelinated neurone) | - | 6 marks |
| b. Describe the structure of axon | - | 6 marks |
| c. State a function of each of the following structures of a cell | - | 1 mark |
| i. Rough endoplasmic reticulum | - | 1 mark |
| ii. The cytoplasm | - | 1 mark |
| iii. Ribosomes | - | 1 mark |
| iv. Centrioles | - | 1 mark |
| d. State any four (4) of the muscles that enclose the abdomen | - | 4 marks |

Question Two

- | | | |
|---|---|---------|
| a. Define the following | | |
| i. Stroke volume | - | 1 mark |
| ii. Diastole | - | 1 mark |
| iii. Systole | - | 1 mark |
| iv. Cardiac output | - | 1 mark |
| v. End diastolic volume | - | 1 mark |
| vi. End systolic volume | - | 1 mark |
| b. Tabulate the differences between arteries and veins. | - | 8 marks |
| Write down three (3) statements each to describe the following: | | |
| i. Mucous membrane | - | 3 marks |
| ii. Serosus membrane | - | 3 marks |

Question Three

Mr. Ameyaw Amoateng a 38 years old man was involved in road traffic accident and had a simple fracture of the femur close to the epicondyle.

- | | | |
|--|---|---------|
| a. Explain how Mr. Ameyaw fracture would be repaired (arrange systematically the stages of fracture repair) – 8marks | - | 8marks |
| b. Outline 4 factors that can cause delay in the healing process of Mr. Ameyaw's fracture | - | 4marks |
| c. State 4 bones that form part of the cranium | - | 4marks |
| d. List the four (4) functions of muscles | - | 4 marks |

Question Four

- | | | |
|--|---|--------|
| a. State 5 factors that can stimulate erythropoietin release from the kidney | - | 5marks |
| b. State and explain the three main epithelial membranes in the human body | - | 9marks |
| c. Differentiate between exocrine and endocrine glands | - | 2marks |
| d. Outline 4 simple epithelial tissues in the body | - | 4marks |

NMTC-BEREKUM-/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-DECEMBER 2016
D19/RM14 RGN111/RMD111 ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY I
TIME ALLOWED: 2HRS

ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate booklet
- Each question carries 20marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.

Question One

- a. Define the term homeostasis - 2marks
- b. With an aid of a simple diagram, explain the feedback mechanism(loops) that the body uses to regulate variables - 5marks
- c. Differentiate between positive and negative feedback mechanisms - 2 marks
- d. State 4 variables that the feedback mechanism regulate in the body - 4 marks
- e. Describe the abdominal cavity - 7marks

Question Two

- a. State the functions of the following cell organelles
- i. Ribosomes - 1mk
 - ii. Smooth endoplasmic reticulum (SER) - 1mk
 - iii. Mitochondria - 1mk
 - iv. Golgi apparatus - 1mk
 - v. Plasma membrane - 3mks
 - vi. Lysosomes - 1mk
- b. Explain the functions of the three (3) main parts of a neuron - 6mks
- c. Describe the three(3) main cartilages in the human body and give two locations where each can be found - 6mks

Question Three

- a. With the aid of a well labeled diagram, describe the characteristics of a synovial joint
- Diagram - 4mks
 - Description - 6mks
- b. Distinguish between true ribs and false ribs - 2mks
- c. Explain five (5) functions of the skeletal system - 5mks
- d. List six (6) bones of the appendicular skeleton - 3mks

Question Four

- a. Describe the flow of blood through the heart - 10mks
- b. Enumerate five(5) factors affecting heart rate - 5mks
- c. Following a motor vehicle accident, a patient is rushed to the emergency department with multiple traumatic injuries, causing severe bleeding. The patient's condition is critical, and there is no time for determining his blood type. What type of blood is transfused, and why?
- 5marks